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Title: Perpetrators and Persecuted in a database on a National Socialist Newspaper and how to reconsider the impact of AI-driven Search

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Abstract

The article examines the ongoing debate at the Hannah Arendt Institute for Totalitarianism Studies (HAIT) concerning the capture, indexing, and publication of information on individuals in the database in the local newspaper of the National Socialist Party in Saxony, published between August 1930 and May 1945. The database was originally established to register articles offering insights into the rise of the National Socialist regime in Saxony, with person indexing limited to party members and prominent regime figures. In 2025, HAIT initiated a review of this practice, which expanded into a broader discussion about the implications of AI-driven search applications for the database. The article mirrors the significant impact of technological advancements on contemporary understandings of data ethics.

Text

In March 2026, the announcement by the U.S. National Archives regarding the online publication of a new set of records generated unprecedented public interest. International media coverage ensued, and the resulting surge in requests temporarily overwhelmed the service. The National Archives had released digitized microfilms of the NSDAP (German National Socialist Party)-membership records, which had been preserved since 1945 as evidence.¹ Following the online release, hundreds of thousands of persons, primarily from Germany and Austria, searched for information about their grandparents and ancestors.² Subsequently, two German publishing houses developed proprietary databases, offering simplified access to these records behind

1 The records with the NAID 12044361 are part of the Record Group 242: National Archives Collection of Foreign Records Seized, <https://catalog.archives.gov/id/12044361>. On the history and access of the files: DPA, ‘Were your grandparents Nazis?: US archive makes millions of NSDAP files available online’, blue news, 18.03.2026, URL: <https://web.archive.org/web/20260318233251/https://www.bluewin.ch/en/news/us-archive-makes-millions-of-nsdap-files-available-online-3151005.html>.

2 Peter Jungblut, ‘Seit der Online-Freigabe: Ansturm auf NSDAP-Mitgliederkartei’, BR24, 18.03.2026, URL: <https://web.archive.org/web/20260318221336/https://www.br.de/nachrichten/kultur/seit-der-online-freigabe-ansturm-auf-nsdap-mitgliederkartei,VED8OGL>; Tageschau.de, ‘Suche im US-Nationalarchiv: Mehr als eine Million Zugriffe auf NSDAP-Mitgliederkartei’ tagesschau.de (18.04.2026), URL: <https://web.archive.org/web/20260418212828/https://www.tagesschau.de/ausland/amerika/usa-nationalarchiv-suche-nsdap-100.html>.

paywalls, in contrast to the time-consuming obtaining of records at the Archive's website. These new services also experienced a significant influx of requests.³

Historians are now confronted by media with questions regarding how the release of these archival records may challenge established historical research on National Socialism – despite at least two decades of research into the role of the population and its complicity –, while some journalists anticipate that this development could foster greater awareness of the dangers posed by far-right extremism.⁴ At the time of writing, Germany is preparing for the likely formation of the first government led by a radical right party since 1945 in at least one Bundesland (federal state).⁵ The redefinition of German history through a new, so-called “patriotic” narrative is a central component of this party's agenda. It remains to be seen whether the public's interest in their families' involvement in National Socialism will contribute to a renewed and strengthened German Erinnerungskultur (Culture of Remembrance), or whether it will instead facilitate the normalization and minimization⁶ of the National Socialist history.

Regardless of the eventual outcome, the ongoing debate about how to interpret the presence or absence of a family member's record in these archives underscores the inherent limitations and ambiguity of archival sources, including membership directories, name lists, and transportation records. Without careful contextualization, such records merely indicate that a name was documented at a specific moment. Nevertheless, the proliferation of openly accessible data, the development of data linkage initiatives, and the use of AI-based search tools have expanded opportunities for non-experts to investigate their family histories. In this situation the HAIT's database appears to become unintentionally a gatekeeper, that keeps information about both the persecuted as individuals known from other databases, and precise descriptions of the enforcement of discrimination and exclusion.

In response to these developments, the Hannah Arendt Institute (HAIT) has begun reassessing its procedures for identifying and naming individuals in its database of articles from the daily NSDAP newspaper “Der Freiheitskampf,” a legacy project of the institute.⁷ Until recently, the policy was to identify and index only members of National Socialist organizations or

3 Bethany Bell, ‘New search engine reveals if ancestors were in Nazi party’, BBC 15.04.2026 URL: <https://web.archive.org/web/20260415215107/https://www.bbc.com/news/articles/cr411ndee7yo>; Jost Maurin, ‘NSDAP-Datenbanken von Spiegel und Zeit: Die Nazi-Dateien sind hilfreich – und keine Gegenwartsflucht’, taz 08.05.2026, URL: <https://web.archive.org/web/20260616152010/https://taz.de/NSDAP-Datenbanken-von-Spiegel-und-Zeit/!6177408>.

4 Anja Reinhardt and Franka Maubach, ‘Familienforschung: Der Umgang mit der NSDAP-Mitgliederkartei’, Podcast Deutschlandfunk Kulturfragen, 04.06.2026, URL: <https://web.archive.org/web/20260604062028/https://www.deutschlandfunk.de/taeter-auf-papier-wie-zuverlaessig-u-wertvoll-ist-die-mitgliedskartei-der-nsdap-100.html>; Jost Maurin, ‘NSDAP-Datenbanken’.

5 As the article was written, the Election in Saxony-Anhalt was still to be held, but polls unanimously show the party AfD (Alternative für Deutschland) not only as leading but gaining a sufficient majority, to form a government even if no other party in the Landtag (state legislature) were to support it.

6 Alexander Gauland and Alice Weidel, ‘Einen Nationalen Aktionsplan Kulturelle Identität auf den Weg bringen’, Deutscher Bundestag, Drucksache 19/28794, 21.04.2021; Matthias Dilling et al., ‘The Populist Radical Right as Memory Entrepreneur?: The Prominence, Sentiment, and Interpretations of History in the German Parliament’, British Journal of Political Science 54, 2024, pp. 1296–1317, DOI: 10.1017/S0007123424000346.

administrative bodies, thereby excluding victims. The project team⁸ had expressed discomfort with this approach for some time, and the policy was not uniformly implemented. The call for the conference in Mainz in November 2025 prompted an open discussion and the initiation of a formal review process. This process led to a fundamental reconsideration of the database's function as a commented register, particularly as AI-driven search applications and Chatbots are growing a new interface for retrieving, modifying, and reusing information from the web. As of the writing of this article, HAIT has not yet determined the final course of action, but the review has already yielded a clearer understanding of previous selection and indexing practices. Accordingly, this article outlines the issues and concerns at HAIT and presents preliminary considerations for future action.

The first part of this article provides information on the project and the database, outlines the problem as it was until very recently understood at HAIT, and presents relevant examples. The second part turns to the still-to-be-digested impact of AI-driven search on the question of how to include the persecuted ethically and how to make data accessible to AI.

The Project “Database of the NS-newspaper ‘Der Freiheitskampf’”

Saxony, in the eastern part of Germany, played a particular role in the history of National Socialism. During the Weimar Republic, the overwhelmingly Protestant region experienced political turmoil and strong support for social democracy and left-wing political movements. In the late 1920s, the situation changed, and the national socialist ideology gained influence. Under the lead of, among others, the deeply anti-Semitic regional leader Martin Mutschmann, Saxony turned into one of the regions with a very high approval rate for the NSDAP.⁹ This transformation leaves historians with questions, or as an early report on the HAIT's project states, “This development is both disturbing and interesting...” (“Diese Entwicklung ist befremdlich und interessant zugleich...”).¹⁰ Research on the reasons for Saxony's political turnaround and the specific context involved is particularly hard due to the covering up of traces by the Germans in the final days of the national socialist regime and the massive air raids of

7 Most of the literature on the project I will refer to is in German; the English-language article by Christoph Hanzig, Martin Munke, and Michael Thoß, published in 2022, summarizes very well all the detailed literature. It might well serve to follow along the description of the history of the database; Christoph Hanzig et al., ‘Digitising and Presenting a Nazi Newspaper: The example Der Freiheitskampf’, Estelle Bunout et al., ed., *Digitised Newspapers – A New Eldorado for Historians?: Reflections on Tools, Methods and Epistemology* (Oldenburg, 2022), pp. 153–172, DOI: 10.1515/9783110729214-008.

8 The team was in 2025 to summer 2026: Christoph Hanzig, Sebastian Rab, Henrik Selle, and Josephine Templer as editors; Francesca Weil and the author as project managers. Michael Thoß, a former editor, working on an offspring of the project, took part in the discussions together with Christoph and Sebastian. They offered the author many insights into their years of experience as editors.

9 Markus Fischer, ‘Neue Perspektiven auf die sächsische NS-Presse. Eine Aufarbeitung des NSDAP-Organs “Der Freiheitskampf”’, *Neues Archiv für sächsische Geschichte*, 84, 2013, pp. 275–276, DOI: 10.52411/nasg.Bd.84.1013.S.275-293.

10 Christiane Steigel and Manja Preissler, ‘Das Projekt: Datenbank zur Dresdner Tageszeitung der NSDAP für den Gau Sachsen „Der Freiheitskampf“: Einführung in die Nutzung der Datenbank’. Zenodo. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20688383.

1945, especially the bombardment of Dresden, the capital of Saxony. Source material is therefore extremely rare. In this situation, historians at the HAIT decided as early as 2009 to catalog articles and reports of the party's newspaper "Der Freiheitskampf. Amtliche Tageszeitung der NSDAP Gau Sachsen" (from now it will be referred to as "Der Freiheitskampf") for offering a kind of substitute for the lost archival records.¹¹

Considering the newspaper's unequivocally partial perspective, the researchers decided to focus on recording information about the organizational development of the NSDAP and public institutions – as "Der Freiheitskampf" offers insights into a less uniformly linear but more complex and multifaceted history, that counteracts a streamlined narrative of the governed and their rulers.¹² This objective continues to be pursued to this day, despite many minor variations in methodology.¹³ As understanding grew of the intertwining of National Socialism with various aspects of public life in Saxony, and as the newspaper itself underwent a profound transformation—from the party organ of a radical political movement to a full-fledged daily newspaper with a broad readership from 1933 on¹⁴—the database editors steadily expanded the range of articles to be included. In order to organize the mass of entries they deployed keywords (92 as of June 2026), the indexing of a sample of places (318) and started as a subproject an inventory of persons mentioned in the newspaper in connection to the party's activities (mostly Parteigenossen (party members)) and the changes in the staff of public administration, government agencies as well as leading characters of academia and culture conforming to National Socialism.¹⁵ Until today, the editors read every issue, made available by the Sächsische Landesbibliothek – Staats- und Universitätsbibliothek Dresden (Saxon State and University Library Dresden (SLUB))¹⁶ as digitized microfilm, and decide which articles should be cataloged.

11 Markus Fischer, 'Neue Perspektiven'; Martin Munke et al., '„Der Freiheitskampf“: Digitisation and Indexing of a National Socialist Daily'. IFLA News Media Section Satellite conference 2017 (2017), URL: <https://nbn-resolving.de/urn:nbn:de:bsz:14-qucosa2-164012>; Christoph Hanzig et al., 'Das Datenbankprojekt des Hannah-Arendt-Instituts für Totalitarismusforschung zur sächsischen NS-Tageszeitung „Der Freiheitskampf“', *Denkströme. Journal der Sächsischen Akademie der Wissenschaften*, 22, 2020, pp. 101–108, http://repo.saw-leipzig.de:80/pubman/item/escidoc:55058/component/escidoc:55057/denkstroeme-heft22_101-108_hanzig_kaeseberg_thoß.pdf; Christoph Hanzig and Michael Thoß, 'Nationalsozialistische Presse als digitale Quelle für die Geschichtswissenschaft', Martin Munke, ed., *Landes- und Regionalgeschichte digital: Angebote – Bedarfe – Perspektiven* (Dresden and Berlin, 2022), pp. 115–131, DOI 10.25366/2021.25.

12 Martin Munke et al., „Der Freiheitskampf“, p. 5.

13 The project was initiated at HAIT by Thomas Widera, who worked for several years on different projects at HAIT without ever holding a permanent position. Until the recording of the newspaper became part of the project "Virtuelle Archive für die geisteswissenschaftliche Forschung" (Christoph Hanzig et al., 'Das Datenbankprojekt'), funded from May 2017 to December 2019 by the State of Saxony, it was understaffed, and work was often run by just a handful of student assistants. As might be expected, this very difficult situation affected data quality and led to a lack of documentation. Thanks to the funding, a dedicated team has been working together on the database since 2016. The team members have established their own quality assurance procedures, such as the dual-review principle. After 2019, HAIT decided to finance the completion of the database using its own funds.

14 Martin Munke et al., '„Der Freiheitskampf“', *ibid.*; Markus Fischer, 'Neue Perspektiven', p. 277–279, footnote 9; pp. 280–291.

15 Key figures of the Third Reich, such as Himmler, are indexed in the database only if they appear in a context densely related to events in Saxony. An example is the propaganda appearance of Hermann Göring in 1936 at Dresden.

16 Markus Fischer, 'Neue Perspektiven', p. 278.

For each entry, they write a brief summary, assign keywords, and, where possible, link it to the biographical database and the project's gazetteer. While working on an internal database, they publish the entries in the online database as soon as they have recorded all the issues for a given year.

The individuals in the dataset

To date, approximately 31,000 entries mostly refer to an article or a brief news item in "Der Freiheitskampf" from August 1930—the newspaper's first issue—through December 1939. For two-thirds of them (20,743 entries), at least one person is listed. The index of persons comprises 2795 records.¹⁷ Only 153 (approx. 5 %) of the recorded individuals are mentioned in more than 50 records on articles in the newspaper, while 53 % are indexed in only two to ten. The project members strive to index individuals who appear across a series of events or articles. Nevertheless, currently 486 persons are not linked to more than one entry. As data collection is still ongoing, there might be further mentions in the issues of 1940 to 1945.

For some years now there is an ongoing work to reference the indexed individuals with the GND – authority files of the Deutsche Nationalbibliothek (Germany's National library) – and very recently the team decided to publish data at FactGrid.¹⁸ 24 % (660) of individuals could so far be identified at the GND and the majority of them is referenced in more than ten entries, a figure that mirrors their elevated role in national socialist Saxony. Still, these efforts were deployed solely to improve data quality and database retrieval.

Many of the persons with a low frequency of appearance were of importance only on a regional or local scale, for example, the three times indexed Anni Lehmann, a local leader of Jungmädelbund (Young Girls' League (JM), a section of the Bund Deutscher Mädels (BDM)). She is mentioned in three datasets capturing articles on activities of the party's youth organization: an article describing a promotional event of the organization (published on March 15, 1938), an article on an educational event of the JM (published on October 20, 1938) and a notice about the promotion of Anni Lehmann and two further individuals in the hierarchy (printed on November 11, 1939).¹⁹ Until now, she can not be linked to an authority file in the GND or an item in FactGrid. Further information concerning her has so far not been obtained.²⁰ Others indexed at the HAIT's database were key figures of National Socialism and the Third Reich in Saxony. Examples are Gauleiter (regional leader) and Reichsstatthalter (Reich governor) Martin Mutschmann, who is

17 The numbers are referring to all datasets captured so far, and that differs from the counts of the so far released publicly available website.

18 The project's page at FactGrid: https://database.factgrid.de/wiki/FactGrid:NS-Tageszeitung_%22Der_Freiheitskampf%22, accessed 14.06.2026.

19 Database entries: ID 67412, ID 76383, and ID 63259.

20 It is worth noticing that currently (May 2026), the project has not begun to carry out research into the NSDAP-membership records.

assigned to 2,464 datasets, or Hellmuth Peitsch, a leading Saxon official of the Deutsche Arbeitsfront (German Workers' Front (DAF)), with 604 entries linked to him.²¹

Apart from very few prominent individuals, to whom the journalists referred several times as enemies of the national socialist movement and after 1933 as enemies of the German "Volksgemeinschaft", most victims of National Socialism are, if at all, only once or twice briefly mentioned by the newspaper. Therefore, their indexing in the database would not affect retrieval, nor would it meet the research objective. Still, the persecuted are mentioned to some extent in the database in the short descriptions of the referred article. Some of them are named; for others, the entries include information about the individual's naming in the newspaper. Over time and as staff changed, the members of the database project applied different approaches without documenting them. Before analyzing the different kind of entries in the database, it is important to understand the context in which the individuals – the persecuted and oppressed – appear in the newspaper. As stated earlier, the newspaper underwent the first major transformation in scope in 1933, with the beginning of the National Socialist reign in Germany. Before 1933 the newspaper agitated the party's members and supporters of National Socialist ideology. Coverage of violent encounters with political enemies as well as publicity against politicians and the state order, which were perceived as corrupt and malicious, made up a significant part of daily issues. After 1933, it was, however, not so much about revenge as about spelling out the national socialist ideology, while at the same time luring the public into the new regime and adopting the party's organization for their new role. The newspaper's issues grew in size, and sections such as financial reports and special supplements for women gained in importance.²² Many of the articles originated with news agencies and were printed *verbatim* by competing media outlets (we will return to this later). Another transformation occurred after the onset of war, beginning in 1940. Within this chronological framework, there were many other shifts that shaped the newspaper's content, but describing them in detail would go beyond the scope of this article; instead it is important to notice that the database reflects those shifts but is biased by its specific scope.

The Persecuted and records on acts of "racial defilement"

The newspaper holds articles mentioning individuals who became victims of the national socialist state and ideology, but were in fact perceived as political enemies, criminals and those who were despised of other reasons. Jews and people of Jewish descent for example were portrayed, on the one hand, as a dehumanized collective enemy, but on the other hand as individuals, for example, in news coverage of criminal cases and court proceedings. Many of those cases involved crimes that would still be considered criminal offenses under current law,

21 Released datasets connected to Mutschmann and Peitsch are to be called by
<https://hait.tu-dresden.de/ext/forschung/der-freiheitskampf.asp#?person=Mutschmann,%20Martin>;
[https://hait.tu-dresden.de/ext/forschung/der-freiheitskampf.asp#?person=Peitsch,%20Hellmuth%20\(Gauobmann%20NSBO/DAF\)](https://hait.tu-dresden.de/ext/forschung/der-freiheitskampf.asp#?person=Peitsch,%20Hellmuth%20(Gauobmann%20NSBO/DAF))

22 Martin Munke et al., „Der Freiheitskampf“, pp. 4–6.

like fraud or burglary. It is hardly surprising that the tone of those reports is not neutral and that the descriptions of the alleged acts draw on anti-Semitic stereotypes, as examples will show, or tie to eugenics. Other criminal offenses and administrative violations existed only because of laws introduced by the national socialist government, and today the “crime” lies not in violating those inhumane and disgraceful laws but in their former existence.

A very prominent example is the act of “Rassenschande” (racial defilement), which came into existence in September 1935 as part of the “Gesetz zum Schutz des deutschen Blutes und der deutschen Ehre” (Law for the Protection of German Blood and German Honor). It prohibited any sexual relationship between Germans who were believed to meet the (pseudo-)biological standard of “Germanic” ancestry and individuals who were not classified as such. The database captured such coverage by tagging them as (in most cases) “anti-semitism” in addition to other keywords like “racism”, “criminal court proceedings”. A survey in spring 2026 shows 39 data records citing articles in which racial defilement was mentioned as an act.²³ The coverage of racial defilement in “Der Freiheitskampf” and the HAIT’s database as a tool for researching the enforcement of the law interested the project members since early on, as publications prove.²⁴ To some surprise, the entries demonstrate a variety of approaches to if and how to give details about the suspected or convicted perpetrators. To illustrate this, some entries from the database will be repeated as they are, without displaying the newspaper texts here. The first exposure of people found to be guilty and therefore taken into “Schutzhaft”²⁵ by the SS in 1934 (!) occurred on 18 July 1935, on the front page of “Der Freiheitskampf” with a list of 15 incidents. All of them, with the names of the involved, their professions (and often professional interrelations), as well as their place of living. The entry in the database refers to it rather briefly and without repeating any of the names:

Entry Database ID 24064²⁶: “A list of individuals who have been placed in protective custody since late 1934 for ‘racially defiling relations with Jews’. The Jewish partners were also sent to the concentration camp Sachsenburg, and the foreigners among them were expelled from the Reich. ...”

In 1938 at Dresden, two consecutive trials of a Hungarian man took place, who was charged with “racial defilement”. The man's biography made him a target for reporting that drew on anti-Semitic stereotypes. In the database, two articles were recorded with biographical details (date

23 Database “Der Freiheitskampf” search term “Rassenschande”, <https://hait.tu-dresden.de/ext/forschung/der-freiheitskampf.asp#?terms=Rassenschande>, accessed 16.05.2026.

24 Martin Munke et al., ‘„Der Freiheitskampf“’, pp. 4–6; Christoph Hanzig and Michael Thoß, ‘Nationalsozialistische Presse’, pp. 122–129.

25 “Schutzhaft” was a detention by the SS without trial, typical during the early years of the Nazi regime. In the HAIT’s database, the term is placed in quotation marks to highlight the cynical attempt to disguise the unlawful practice.

26 Database “Der Freiheitskampf” ID 24064, <https://hait.tu-dresden.de/ext/forschung/der-freiheitskampf.asp#?id=24064>, accessed 14.06.2026; To this date (summer 2026), the given IDs serve as permanent identifiers for the entry, but without capturing their versioning, therefore citing the database should include the day of accessing the entry.

and place of birth), but the name the newspaper provided has not been included. To maintain the relationship between the two entries, the latter refers to the first.

Entry Database ID 65979²⁷: “A detailed article on a criminal trial before the 30. Strafkammer [court of jurisdiction, comment author] against a Jew born on January 22, 1884, in Tecs (Hungary). He had been charged with “racial defilement” and sentenced to two years in prison and three years of loss of civil rights. The article describes not only the alleged “crime” of the “delinquent,” but also the defendant’s past in Hungary, where, as the FHK [newspaper “Der Freiheitskampf”, comment author] writes, he covered himself with the “[disguise] of the ‘Christian faith.’””

Entry Database ID 83975²⁸: “Report on a trial before the 30. Strafkammer des Landgerichts Dresdens [court of jurisdiction, comment author] regarding repeated ‘racial defilement’ against a 44-year-old Jewish man, who was sentenced there to two years in prison. For the first conviction by the same court, see ID 65979.”

The man was murdered at the Sachsenhausen concentration camp in September 1942.²⁹

A different approach was followed for a man who was found guilty and for whom the newspaper reported on a long-term relationship with the intention of getting married to a Jewish woman. In this case, the editors decided to provide all the details of the individual that would allow for identification.

Entry Database ID 71004³⁰: “An article about the sentence of one year and three months’ imprisonment handed down by the Große Strafkammer of Landgericht Leipzig [court of jurisdiction, comment author] to Otto Schäfer, born in Borna on May 16, 1901, for ‘racial defilement in two instances’, because he had maintained a long-term relationship with a “Jewish woman” even after the Blutschutzgesetz [law of 1935, author] went into effect.”

The coverage was less hostile than the one reported before, so was this a reason for the editors to behave less “protective” and give all details? That seems not to have been the motivation for the disclosure shown by the following record referring to another coverage of a verdict in 1937.

Entry Database ID 64150³¹: “Report on a sentence handed down by the Leipziger Landgerichts [court of jurisdiction, comment author] against a man and his subtenant for racial defilement. In 1934, they had begun a relationship with their Jewish housekeeper and continued it even after the racial laws were enacted in 1935. The court sentenced both men

27 Database “Der Freiheitskampf” ID 65979, <https://hait.tu-dresden.de/ext/forschung/der-freiheitskampf.asp?id=65979>, accessed 12.06.2026.

28 Database “Der Freiheitskampf” ID 83975, <https://hait.tu-dresden.de/ext/forschung/der-freiheitskampf.asp?id=83975>, accessed 12.06.2026.

29 Database names Bela Denes, <https://collections.yadvashem.org/en/names/7458273>, accessed 12.06.2026.

30 Database “Der Freiheitskampf” ID 71004, <https://hait.tu-dresden.de/ext/forschung/der-freiheitskampf.asp?id=71004>, accessed 13.06.2026.

31 Database “Der Freiheitskampf” ID 64150, <https://hait.tu-dresden.de/ext/forschung/der-freiheitskampf.asp?id=64150>, accessed 13.06.2026.

to prison terms of nine and seven months, respectively. The author of the article criticizes the lenient sentences: ‘It is regrettable that these unprincipled young men got off so lightly, having placed themselves outside the Volksgemeinschaft [ethnic community, comment author] through their behavior.’”

The very short entry (ID 64804³²) on the article of yet another verdict on racial defilement offers one more solution. Here, the dataset gives the last name and the place of living (Großröhrsdorf). But Großröhrsdorf had a population of about 8,000 in 1925 – a figure that really does not allow for “anonymity”.

This small randomized sample demonstrates that there was apparently no agreed-upon standard for recording such cases in the database at HAIT. It is worth noticing that at the beginning of the reassessment of practices following the conference in November 2025, the current team expressed their confidence that names, addresses, and dates of birth had, in fact, never been entered, with the exception of one editor who explained having started to do so some time ago, in awareness of breaking a policy. It is widely acknowledged at HAIT that former editors took great care to avoid re-victimizing the people mentioned in “Der Freiheitskampf” and therefore agreed not to facilitate their identification. By neither entering the names and addresses in the database nor repeating derogatory terminology without quotation marks, the editors refrained from re-enacting the former discriminatory assignment. This policy was understood and shared as part of an ethics-based, responsibility-driven practice, though only partially applied. This gap between theory, or more precisely, unwritten policy and daily doing is maybe less astonishing when taking into consideration that the vast majority of articles the editors selected, indexed, and summarized are of a different nature: less than 0,5 % of all entries refer to the coverage of articles on individuals suspected of having committed an act of “racial defilement”. Encountering them, the researchers may have made decisions largely upon the situation at hand rather than in awareness of a high-level policy. What held true for all was that the individuals were not to be included in the registry with the perpetrators, party members, and officials of the regime. The one person of the project who decided to follow along a different road did this because, to her, the (not strictly adhered to) policy of anonymity to the persecuted felt from an ethical point of view wrong, because anonymization would do less to protect the victims of re-enacting an act of discrimination than to prevent users of the database from becoming aware of the true impact of that injustice. That said, the purpose was not to enable identification—birth dates and addresses are crucial for that; anyone who wanted to find out more about a person could look up the information in the newspaper themselves, as the editor argued, because it had never been part of the project’s objectives to capture the identities of the persecuted.

This argumentation leans into the way memorial sites try to engage with visitors today. By contrasting individual life stories with factual information about historical events, visitors are

32 Database “Der Freiheitskampf” ID 64804, <https://hait.tu-dresden.de/ext/forschung/der-freiheitskampf.asp?id=64804>, accessed 13.06.2026.

encouraged to recognize for themselves the inhumane consequences of segregation laws, their enforcement, and the passivity of the majority. Nevertheless, the HAIT's database is a tool for researchers³³ and not an offer of a memorial site. Displaying an individual's name and details is not the same as a carefully researched biography. Memorial sites are very mindful of encountering the transformation of the persecuted from individuals to stereotypical figures or even dehumanized objects by showing them as fellow human beings with all their strengths, aspirations, weaknesses, and their social backgrounds. If one limits the focus to the database and the perspectives of German researchers – who, in terms of statistics, are largely descendants of the former majority society – the approach taken so far could be considered as the more ethical one. Again, at a closer look, a more nuanced picture emerges, as another dataset corroborates.

In September 1936, “Der Freiheitskampf” as well as several other local media outlets published a brief note on the arrest of a man named Chaim Großbauch, a 48-year-old resident of Dresden, on charges of “racial defilement”.³⁴ After being held in custody for seven months, he was finally sentenced on April 16, 1937, to one year in prison at the Zwickau Penitentiary.³⁵ The coverage of the newspaper “Dresdner Neueste Nachrichten” of the court trial portrayed the convicted as a defiant foreigner, born in Kolomya, living in two consecutive romantic relationships and who was temporarily not residing in Germany.³⁶ Another more detailed and even more hostile article appeared in the regional *Mitteldeutsche Nationalzeitung*, offered with full text by the Press portal of the German National Library³⁷ – after checking a disclaimer, that informs users about press under the regime of National Socialism.³⁸ The publication “Buch der Erinnerung”³⁹ (Book of remembrance) offers a short biography that reveals how much even this factual summary of the coverage was biased. First of all, his full given name was Karl Chaim, which shows, he aligned

33 Martin Munke et al., „Der Freiheitskampf“, p. 6: “Die Datenbank zum “Freiheitskampf” [...] richtet sich in erster Linie an Wissenschaftlerinnen und Wissenschaftler, die sich mit der Etablierung und Festigung nationalsozialistischer Machtstrukturen in Sachsen beschäftigen.” (The database on the “Der Freiheitskampf” [...] is primarily intended for scholars studying the National Socialist Party's rise to power and its consolidation in Saxony).

34 Database “Der Freiheitskampf” ID 54002, <https://hait.tu-dresden.de/ext/forschung/der-freiheitskampf.asp?id=54002>, accessed 07.11.2025.

35 Registry of items at the Saxony States' archive: “Bestand 30071 Zuchtahaus Zwickau, 3 Gefangenenakten”, file “4244 Chaim Großbauch”, <https://www.archiv.sachsen.de/archiv/bestand.jsp?guid=153a0fe3-ea71-46ae-a7c6-b76b82cee33d>, accessed 10.06.2026.

36 Anonymus, ‘Richter und Angeklagte: Der Rassenschänder’. *Dresdner neueste Nachrichten Nr. 90*, 17.4.1937 (Dresden), p. 6. URL: <https://www.deutsche-digitale-bibliothek.de/newspaper/item/BO53JOZLIC25M3JJCJTE7EIHSMSNHT5I?issuepage=6>.

37 Anonymus, ‘Ostjude als Rassenschänder’, *Mitteldeutsche Nationalzeitung*, 19.04.1937, p.3. <https://www.deutsche-digitale-bibliothek.de/newspaper/item/BSP7HJEVTCYRTRKVRCDWFE0077GQ4PC?issuepage=3>.

38 The disclaimer offers a link to the online-exhibition on NS-press by the German National Library: ‘Presse in der Zeit des Nationalsozialismus’, URL: <https://ausstellungen.deutsche-digitale-bibliothek.de/ns-presse>, accessed 12.05.2026.

39 Gabriele Atanassow, *Buch der Erinnerung. Juden in Dresden: deportiert, ermordet, verschollen (1933–1945)* (Leipzig 2025 [1st 2nd edition]), p. 193.

himself to the place he was living in. Furthermore, we learn about his brother, Aaron Großbauch, who made his living in Dresden since World War I and was a father of four, and we will return to him later on. Karl Chaim Großbauch had a regular profession and was employed in Dresden. In 1938, it is assumed in February following his imprisonment, he was expelled to Poland. His further fate remains unclear, as he disappeared and is indexed at Yad Vashem as a victim of the Shoah.⁴⁰ The practice of omitting the “Germanic” given first name Karl is inevitably connected to the exclusion, segregation and consequently extermination of people of Jewish descent. By anonymizing the entry regarding the trial of Karl Chaim Großbauch, the HAITs’ database in fact mitigates precisely what the entry is intended to highlight: the pre-staging of genocide. By reproducing the name as found in the newspaper, the entry echoes the discriminatory act. It is also noteworthy that the additional detail—that the man has a brother with a family in Dresden—creates a sense of involvement in the man’s and his family’s fate. It is indeed the effect described earlier regarding the display of biographies at memorial sites. The example seems to make a strong case for further investigation into each individual in the entries concerning at least racial defilement, and for taking at least the same efforts for their identification and linking as are carried out for individuals like the aforementioned Anni Lehmann and Hellmut Peitsch.

Why the progress of AI-driven search matters now

Although presented as given practice, the exposure of the biographies of individuals persecuted during National Socialism in Germany is far more complex. It is related, firstly, to the different post-war societies in the former German Democratic Republic (GDR) and the Federal Republic of Germany (FRG), secondly, to the different groups of victims and their post-war (non)identity, and thirdly, to generational change as well as societal and digital transformation.⁴¹ This is a vast topic to even touch upon in this article; still, it must be acknowledged that the debate on data ethics regarding the database at stake takes place in an ever-shifting landscape. Currently, the most dynamic aspects from the authors’ perspective are datafication, Linked Data, and AI.

AI matters here in its directions of generative and of analytical AI.⁴² The dissemination of ChatGPT in 2024, generative AI turned over within less than five years, and the way in which many of us obtain information. Since then, Google has deployed Gemini and made major changes regarding the ranking of search results.⁴³ The intention is to keep users on the Google

40 Yad Vashem, Database Names, ID 13487262; <https://collections.yadvashem.org/en/names/13487262>, accessed 30.10.2025.

41 Andreas Nachama and Uwe Neumärker, ‘Gedenken und Datenschutz’, *Topographie des Terrors* 12 (Berlin, 2017); Aleida Assmann, ‘Das neue Unbehagen an der Erinnerungskultur: eine Intervention’ (München, 2020); Wolfgang Benz, ‘Zukunft der Erinnerung das deutsche Erbe und die kommende Generation’ (München 2025); Susanne Urban, ‘The Shoah, Postcolonialism, and *Historikerstreit* 2.0: Germany’s Past in Its Present’, *Israel Journal of Foreign Affairs*, 16/1, pp. 83–97, DOI: 10.1080/23739770.2022.2065798.

42 For a comprehensive definition of the difference, see: Felix Stalder, ‘Vantablack. Generative AI as premonition’, Blog ‘n.n. Notes and Nodes by Felix Stalder’, published 28.03.2025, URL: <https://web.archive.org/web/20260413085636/https://felix.openflows.com/articles/vantablack-generative-ai-as-premonition.html>.

43 Rebecca Schneid, ‘Google Shifts to AI Search, Heralding Major Change in How People Use the Internet’, *Time*, published 20.05.2026, URL: <https://time.com/article/2026/05/20/google-search-ai-internet>, accessed

site instead of distributing them to the ranked sites. To foster this, Google integrated ChatBot functionality into its AI Overview, so instead of restarting the search with a new phrase, users can prompt follow-ups. Various posts on social media and blogs from tech businesses indicate that a high ranking in search results does not align with being mentioned and linked in the AI's output. Instead, it seems that provenance, uniqueness, and perhaps diversity of media (text, images, audio, etc.), as well as AI-optimized texts, are criteria for display in the AI Overview.⁴⁴ Another feature that might have a huge impact is AI agents, which monitor and report changes in the results to a once given request.⁴⁵

Entering “Chaim Großbauch” into the Google search box⁴⁶ in June 2026 generates an AI Overview referencing the aforementioned article from the daily newspaper *Dresdner Nachrichten*. Google Gemini 3.5 extracts biographical data (place and date of birth) from the article and supplements it with entries from *genealogy.net*.⁴⁷ The result contextualizes the act of racial defilement as part of the repression of Jewish people, but does not reference the accessible registry of Zwickau penitentiary at the Saxon state archive, nor does it reproduce information from the database Names provided by Yad Vashem. The source, *Dresdner Nachrichten* (DN), is labeled as NS-press, which obscures the distinction between a controlled, censored press, as in the case of DN, and a party's official mouthpiece, such as “*Der Freiheitskampf*.” Adjusting the default search parameters for geographical region produces markedly different results; for example, selecting the US as the target region yields only data from *Genealogy.net*. While it may be tempting to focus on output variations or misconceptions in AI-generated results—potentially reinforcing the view of AI as a “stochastic parrot” and emphasizing the distinctiveness of historiographic research⁴⁸—the results instead raise urgent ethical questions regarding practices at HAIT, as well as at memorial sites and archives.

When it comes to victims of the Shoah, our example reveals that training data and the behavioral fit of generative AI applications provide a quite reliable framing of information, even if obtained from the perpetrator's perspective. The risk of perpetuating stereotypes, therefore, seems to be in no relation to the problem that multiple sites repeating the few known facts, in

12.06.2026; Elizabeth Reid, ‘A new Era of AI search’, Google: The Keyword, published 19.5.2026, URL: <https://web.archive.org/web/20260520000912/https://blog.google/products-and-platforms/products/search/search-io-2026>.

44 See as *pars pro toto*: Dipti Padalkar, ‘E-E-A-T for AI Content: How Google Evaluates AI-Written Pages in 2026’, Trusted AI SEO, published 25.12.2025, URL: <https://web.archive.org/web/20260621102251/https://trustedaiseo.com/e-e-a-t-for-ai-content/>.

45 Elizabeth Reid, ‘A new Era of AI search’.

46 With all parameters unchanged against the default.

47 *Genealogy.net*, ‘Karl Chaim Großbauch’, URL: https://ofb.genealogy.net/famreport.php?ofb=juden_nw&ID=I328049, accessed 17.06.2026.

48 Thorsten Hiltmann, ‘Hermeneutik in Zeiten der KI: Large Language Models als hermeneutische Instrumente in den Geschichtswissenschaften’, Gerhard Schreiber and Lukas Ohly, ed., *KI:Text* (Berlin, 2024), pp. 201–232, DOI. 10.1515/9783111351490-014; Sibylle Krämer, ‘Der Stachel des Digitalen: Geisteswissenschaften und Digital Humanities’ (Berlin 2025); Max Beck, ‘Die Mensch-Maschine. Zur Kritik der Anthropomorphisierung von Large Language Models’ *Merkur* 80/923, April 2026, pp.93–98; James Somers, ‘Und wenn sie doch denkt?’, *Merkur* 80/923, April 2026, pp. 20–33.

the use case, the place and date of birth, often without firstly making explicit the sources and almost always the voids, and secondly, without providing data targeting specifically machines and technologies of retrieval. Traditionally, the institutions that maintain the databases have lent them credibility. However, in the logic of, for example, Google's AI application, it seems to be more relevant that the specific piece of information provided by the database is unique and most favorably backed by a citation. The aim is to exclude generic (and AI-generated) content. Providing machine-readable, AI-optimized information also entails explicitness about voids. Instead of leaving the place and date of death blank in our use case, a statement should detail the lack of information, or the empty fields should not be created in the first place. Leaving the combination of different data sources concerning the victims to AI is to deliver them to the unification and homogenization inherent to generative AI. In consequence, it deprives them of their history, instead of remembering the victims as individuals and, by exposing the vast unknowns surrounding their fates, to keep the crime of extermination ever in our memories⁴⁹ Instead of publishing databases for visitor lookup on the website of a memorial site or a research institute, machines could be integrated as multipliers of curated, trusted information for AI agents and digital research tools.

This approach is in line with the "collections-as-data" initiative and especially implication 11 "Collections-as-data stewards should design access with appropriate consideration of data consumption by artificial intelligence or other technologies."⁵⁰ is relevant to how victims are captured in HAIT's database, as well as to how the project can contribute to a more suitable and precise representation of them in AI-driven search applications. As a consequence, the perception of the project members' roles as editors will likely shift to encompass aspects of data stewardship. Nevertheless, that turn will perhaps be more a clarification of the responsibilities that the researchers have long anticipated, as the description of the established workflows showed. The field of work would entail an intensified publishing information to FactGrid, a community-driven database based on Wikibase. To enhance the training data for generative AI, datasets should be prepared for publication on Zenodo, a step that would require further research on best practices. Another major contribution to meet the objective of collections-as-data might be the publication of the database entries alongside the text of the annotated newspaper's articles, resulting from layout segmentation and text recognition. In winter 2025/26, the project IDOHIST⁵¹ at HAIT began testing whether it is possible to obtain information on the organized social activities of the NSDAP-Ortsgruppen (local party organization units).⁵² Thanks to the groundbreaking development in the field of text recognition⁵³ by analytical AI and

49 The idea of coping with the voids – the lack of images, documents, and tangible objects – as a practice of remembering and mourning genocides was part of a keynote of Thomas Ebbrecht-Hartmann at the Conference 'KI schreibt Geschichte', 17–18 June 2026, Gedenkstätte Haus der Wannseekonferenz.

50 Thomas Padilla et al., 'Vancouver Statement on Collections as Data', Zenodo, 13.09.2023, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.8342171, p. 4.

51 <https://idohist.org>, accessed 16.06.2026.

52 This is pursued by Michael Thoß and Gesine Janke.

53 Lorenz Dändliker et al., 'Ad fontes, Automated Text Recognition: – Making (Handwritten) Documents Accessible', CC-BY, 2025. URL:<https://web.archive.org/web/20260520193529/https://www.adfontes.uzh.ch/en/tutorium/>

the commitment to Open Science by the developers of Eynollah⁵⁴ at the Staatsbibliothek zu Berlin (Berlin State Library) the IDOHIST-team was able to demonstrate the general viability of the approach even with modest computational power.⁵⁵ It is now up to the team of the database on “Der Freiheitskampf” to decide whether the technology should be applied and whether the database entries should be created together with generative KI, with the researchers as “human in the loop”. Here again, the role would shift to that of a data steward focused on preparing reliable, ethical data.

“Was my relative a Nazi?” or “What happened to my relatives”

2025 marked the 80th anniversary of the liberation of Auschwitz, the siege of Berlin, and the complete surrender of the “Third Reich”. But as the opening remarks illustrated, in Germany, the remembrance is an ongoing process and (again) a topic of political debate. Analytical AI made millions of files accessible for research. The huge number of requests at the site of the National Archive, as well as at the two databases offered by media outlets, demonstrates that for many, the traditional points of access (archives, museum collections, and memorial sites) are not only less attractive but perhaps not even considered as potential sources for information. Meanwhile, the arrival of AI applications for searching and aligning information results in a new interface to online information; where websites providing databases and collections are treated as sources rather than targets of search requests. To ensure that the stories of vulnerable groups, of dispersed heritage, and of shattered families and friendships are represented, the ongoing practice of providing isolated, often machine-unreadable information should transform into an understanding of machines and AI as assistants for the dissemination of curated, connected, citable data.

The database of the newspaper “Der Freiheitskampf” offers a unique body of work for framing articles on arrests and trials that appeared in multiple newspapers whose texts have already been fully OCR'd and published. Descriptions of how the specific article enforced discrimination and segregation help refine the understanding of the *modus operandi* of National Socialism in everyday life. Adding the victims named in the newspaper to community-driven, machine-readable databases, enriching them with links to the database entries and, wherever possible, adding links to further resources, facilitates the research of relatives. Some press articles may add another piece to the puzzle. Rarely, if at all, the newspaper will provide crucial information on the whereabouts, but it can throw a light on passages. An example is another trial report. It was about Simon Großbauch-Hellenbrandt, one of two nephews of Karl Chaim Großbauch, who

atr/practical-guide-to-atr.

54 Software Eynollah URL: <https://github.com/qurator-spk/eynollah>, v0.8.0, released 11.05.2026; Vahid Rezanezhad et al., ‘Document Layout Analysis with Deep Learning and Heuristics’, Proceedings of the 7th International Workshop on Historical Document Imaging and Processing, (San Jose, 2023), pp. 73–78.

55 The author would like to especially thank the commitment, hard work, and inspiring discussions of Tim Henning (internship in 2023), Jingyi Yu (internship in 2024 to 2025), and Gesine Janke (assistant since 2024). They contributed very much to testing several tools before applying Eynollah at HAIT.

emigrated and survived.⁵⁶ On December 13, the local newspapers of Dresden reported on the verdict of “Symon Großbauch” for fraud. He was sentenced to three months in prison. Among other things, the article stated that the man, after obtaining money through his deception, went to Copenhagen, where he was expelled by the Danish police. The article remarks sarcastically, “But there, he found himself in the same situation as all Jews who had come from Germany as “persecuted” people,..“ (“Dort ging es ihm aber wie allen Juden, die als "Verfolgte" aus Deutschland kommen, ...”). A careful contextualization of the article helps us understand that this may be evidence of an attempt at emigration. It also throws light on the fact that the emigration of Jewish people was a consequence of the repression, not left unnoticed by the people of Dresden, and it seems that the newspapers felt obliged to blur the situation.

56 Gabriele Atanassow, ‘Buch der Erinnerung’, p. 193.